

CAUSE RELATED MARKETING AND CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION: THE MODERATING EFFECT OF SKEPTICISM AND THE MEDIATING ROLE OF BRAND IMAGE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to examine the impact of cause related marketing on purchase intention. The study is quantitative in nature and data was collected through structured questionnaire. The data was analyzed through structural equation model by using AMOS software.

The results reveal that CRM campaign has a positive significant relationship with purchase intentions. It is found that advertising skepticism has no effect on relationship between CRM campaign and purchase intention. Brand image mediates the relationship of CRM campaign and purchase intentions. The study contributes in the scarce literature of cause-related marketing. The study established the role of advertising skepticism and brand image in the cause related marketing programs. The study provides guidelines to the practitioners in order to practice cause-related marketing in their marketing programs.

Keywords: cause-related marketing, purchase intentions, advertising skepticism, brand image.

Introduction:

Over a decade, consumer's shift towards social responsibility has been observed. According to cone 2008, 87% of consumer participants in survey were more interested in purchasing from a brand supporting a cause (Amawate and Deb 2019). In the age of competition, it is necessary for businesses to make strategies to attract more customers. Therefore, all over the world, companies are engaged in promoting a social cause. Cause related marketing (CRM) has become the most practiced type of corporate social responsibility in last few years (Kotler and Lee 2005). (Barone, Norman et al. 2007) defined cause-related marketing as a strategic procedure that is developed to achieve marketing objectives through supporting social causes.

Duncan declared that cause-related marketing is a "mission marketing" in which firm combined the non-profit cause with company business strategies for profit growth (Duncan 1995). This concept of

Cause-related marketing is helpful for entities to buildup long term relations with non-profit organizations and also with customers. Cause-related marketing (CRM) began in 1983 when American Express Company began promoting the specific amount for cause. The fine-grained results of cause-related marketing campaigns help to increase the profits of entity and also help companies to make strategies related to cause-related campaigns that helps out to enlarge the sales and construct a strong positive image of that brand (Shabbir, Kaufmann et al. 2010). Basically, cause-related marketing develops relationship between the company donations and the product sale for the purpose of charity in term of cause (Lucke and Heinze 2015). If different corporations sell the identical products with similar features, consumers prefer to buy those products which donate some charitable amount for social cause (Anghel, Grigore et al. 2011). In present time, consumers don't focus

on price and quantity, so cause-related marketing is effective tactical strategy for promoting social responsibility of companies (Liu and Ko 2011) and vital for companies where they can differentiate their products through social responsibility from competitors (Rashid, Hamidizade et al. 2016).

Cause related marketing is considered as emerging and powerful strategy among marketers. It is practiced by many companies in less developed countries too. Multinational companies also follow this approach for customer retention in developing countries like Pakistan. There are a lot of researches done in developed countries regarding cause-related marketing program such as United-kingdom, America and Europe. Literature revealed that there is deficiency of cause-related marketing researches conducted in developing countries (Shabbir, Kaufmann et al. 2010).

It is newly discovered that if companies use cause-related marketing message in marketing advertisement of product/brand the consumers respond to that brand more positively, as suggested by (Nan and Heo 2007). Some researches revealed that consumers' attitudes to brands are unaffected by the cause-related marketing campaign message. Cause-related marketing is being implemented through several forms (Gupta and Pirsch 2006; Liu and Ko 2011). Recent research studies have shown that, compared to other corporate social responsibility (CSR) actions, such as sponsorship or philanthropy, cause-related marketing activities are more likely to be viewed as doubtful (Sheikh ; Lii and Lee 2012). The skeptic nature of customer may create doubts in the minds of customers, regarding the claims of the advertisement. Cause-related marketing has been characterized as a form of tactical corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Porter and Kramer 2002). Cause-related marketing can be observed as a threefold relationship between consumers, business, and nonprofit organizations (NPO). An example of cause-related marketing is Lipton "Be awake to what really matters" campaign 2016, Lipton Pakistan came up with a new campaign in which they have partnered with The Citizens Foundation to provide free education to students from 10 Schools all across.

The literature needs to fill the gap of insufficient knowledge about understanding of cause-related

marketing in Pakistan. Pakistan is a developing country and has not adopted the modern marketing tactics. It is mandatory to learn the new marketing strategies in order to overcome the competition and gain customer attention. Cause related marketing is proved to be new and useful marketing technique for the businesses. The main objective of this study is to promote the cause related marketing campaign in Pakistan. For this purpose, this research focuses on the purchase intentions of consumers regarding the cause-related marketing campaign. Moreover, research also examines the factors affecting the purchase intention in the context of CRM. Following are the research questions which are going to be answered in this research:

RQ1: What is the relationship between CRM campaign and purchase intentions?

RQ2: Does the relationship between CRM and purchase intention is affected by skepticism?

Literature Review:

Cause related marketing campaign:

In the contemporary era, there is a tough competition between the businesses. Therefore, the businesses pay more attention to their marketing activities. In this day and age, cause related marketing is considered as an emerging tool for companies to join with the causes or charities, with an objective to get the mutual benefits by marketing the products and services. CRM is the most utilized form of corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Kotler and Lee 2008), which involves mutual efforts of a "for profit" business and "not for profit" organization to serve a social cause for a benefit.

The Concept of cause related marketing was inaugurated by American Express in 1983 (Berger, Cunningham et al. 1999). American Express started a CRM campaign for restoration of the statue of liberty. The company pledged to contribute 1% for every card transaction and \$1 for every new card issued during last quarter of 1983. This campaign was proved to be successful. American express donated \$1.7 million to statue of liberty and got business advantages as there was a 28% increase in use of credit cards (Manojkumar and Sharma 2018).

The CRM was defined by Varadarajan and Menon in their pioneer research work on CRM in 1988. Cause-related marketing is defined as: “the process of formulating and implementing marketing activities that are characterized by an offer from firm to contribute a specified amount to a designated cause when customers engage in revenue-providing exchanges that satisfy organizational and individual objectives” (Varadarajan and Menon 1988). According to this definition, CRM is particularly related to a donation from sale of product or service.

In this paper this definition of Cause related marketing is utilized: “CRM is a specific marketing activity in which the firms promises the consumers to donate company resources to a worthy cause for each sold product or service” (Van den Brink, Odekerken-Schröder et al. 2006). In precise words, cause related marketing is considered as marketing with worthy cause (Skory, Repka et al. 2004). The objective of cause related marketing is to bring many potential benefits to the business, like increase in sales, enhanced corporate image, customer retention, and staff loyalty (Vanhamme, Lindgreen et al. 2012). The CRM involves three parties: the company, the cause and the consumer (Pandukuri, Azeem et al. 2017).

An overview of literature on CRM research revealed that the effect of CRM is studied on various consumer behavior variables such as purchase intention (Moosmayer and Fuljahn 2010; Qamar and Lodhi 2013; Hannantyas, Yulianto et al. 2016; Yang and Yen 2018), brand loyalty (Van den Brink, Odekerken-Schröder et al. 2006) and attitude toward CRM (Sheikh ; Cui, Trent et al. 2003). The companies, who are engaged in CRM programs, have a main objective to increase the purchase intentions of consumers (File and Prince 1998). The previous studies have revealed that the impact of CRM campaigns on purchase intentions is significant (Smith and Stodghill 1994; Krol 1996; Murphy 1997; Barone, Norman et al. 2007). On the basis of literature review, we formulate our first our hypothesis as follow:

H1: There is a significant relationship between CRM campaign and consumer purchase intentions.

Skepticism:

The term ‘skepticism’ is originally derived from the Greek word ‘skeptomai’ which means “to consider, to think about and to reflect”(Leonidou and Skarmeas 2017). In term of marketing and advertising, skepticism is considered as likelihood of distrust or disbelief of advertising claims (Obermiller and Spangenberg 1998). In context of CRM, skepticism is tendency of consumer to disbelief the message of advertisement and doubt in the company’s motive of supporting the cause (Friestad and Wright 1994; Mohr, Eroğlu et al. 1998; Webb and Mohr 1998). In CRM campaign, companies make claims about their support for any social or environmental cause but these claims may be perceived in term of skepticism by consumers. The high level of consumer skepticism can lower the trust in CRM campaign claims. The low skeptical consumer has a tendency to believe in the advertising claims (Anuar and Mohamad 2012).

The literature review revealed that some researchers have studied the effect of skepticism (Mohr, Eroğlu et al. 1998). (Mohr, Eroğlu et al. 1998) was the pioneer who studied the effect of skepticism on consumer response and found that skepticism influences the consumer response towards CRM campaign. Previous studies were conducted to study the effect of skepticism on purchase intention in CRM context and found that skepticism can influence purchase intention (Szykman, Bloom et al. 1997; Webb and Mohr 1998; Barone, Norman et al. 2007). On the other hand, some researchers claimed that skepticism cannot affect purchase intention in CRM context (Gupta and Pirsch 2006). The findings of previous studies are not univocal, therefore more investigation is required. On the basis of literature above, we formulate the hypothesis as follow:

H2: Skepticism has a moderating effect on the relationship between CRM campaign and purchase intention.

Brand Image:

Brand image is considered as consumer’s affection and thoughts about a particular brand (Roy and Banerjee 2007). Brand image is defined as the perception of a brand in consumer’s mind by the brand association (Keller 1993). In simple words,

brand image can be expressed as how customer perceives the brand (Aaker 1996). Consumer can perceive the brand image by physical appearance of product (Martinez and De Chernatony 2002). Brand image plays very important role to attract and retain the customers. It makes a perception of brand in mind of consumer and helps him/her to decide whether to choose the brand or not (Dolich 1969). There are some researches on the effect of brand image on consumer purchase decisions (Wang and Tsai 2014; Han 2017; Tariq, Abbas et al. 2017). Brand image influences the consumer to buy the brand because it creates credibility and reputation of brand in eyes of consumer (Wijaya 2013). In this study, the role of brand image between CRM campaign and purchase intention is examined. On the basis of literature review, hypothesis is designed as follow:

H3: Brand image mediates the relationship between the CRM campaign and purchase intentions.

Purchase intentions:

Purchase intention is defined as consumer's inclination toward buying a product or service (Bagozzi and Burnkrant 1985). It is also described as tendency of customer to buy the product after the evaluation of product (Schiffman and Kanuk 2010). The conscious actions of consumer to buy product of particular brand is considered as purchase intention. Purchase intention is a decision making of consumer about the purchase of a products of specific brand (Shah, Aziz et al. 2012). When customer plans to buy a product he/she first wants to evaluate and compare the product by gathering essential and relevant information about the product (Johnson and Russo 1984). There are many studies to examine the impact of CRM campaign on consumer purchase intentions. It is observed that consumers have a positive feeling towards the company that supports any social cause, this affection makes them to buy the product and increase their purchase intentions (Hou, Du et al. 2008). The current study is aimed at studying the impact of CRM campaign on the consumer purchase intentions.

Methodology:

This study is conducted to examine the impact of cause-related marketing campaign on purchase

intention of consumers. Conceptual model is presented as figure 1. In this study we follow the quantitative approach. Data were collected through

the structured questionnaire. All the measures used in the current study are adopted from already developed scales, which based on Five-point likert scale ranging from 1-Strongly Disagree to 5-Strongly Agree. The six-item cause-related marketing campaign scale was adopted from (Ross III, Patterson et al. 1992), four-item skepticism scale was adopted from (Barone, Norman et al. 2007), twelve-item brand image scale was adopted from (del Blanco and Aaker 1995; Lassar, Mittal et al. 1995; Yoo, Donthu et al. 2000) and six-item purchase intentions was adopted from (Hou, Du et al. 2008).

In this study, the “Millions of Meals” campaigns by Pepsi and Lays, were used. The aim of this program is to make millions of meals available to communities that are impacted by Covid-19 outbreak. The brands have partnered with the reputed charitable organizations of Pakistan for the disbursement of these meals nationwide. Pepsi has partnered with Rizq, Orange Tree, Alkhidmat and PPHI as their meal distributing partners in this wonderful initiative. Advertisement is given as Figure 1:

Fig 2: CRM campaign

In this study, data were collected from the people of Lahore who are aware of the brands used in the study. For data collection, online survey software, Google form, was used. The questionnaire was uploaded on Google form and link was shared with respondents through WhatsApp and Messenger applications. The video of campaign was attached with the form. The respondents were asked to see the video and fill the questionnaire. Data were collected by using the simple random sampling. The total respondents were 143, who filled the questionnaire completely. For data analysis, Statistical package for social science (SPSS) and Analysis of moment structure (AMOS) soft wares were used. The two-step

approach used that is recommended by (Hair et al. 1998). The measurement model was evaluated to check the validity and reliability of each construct. Various techniques were used such as exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis. The structural model was examined to test the hypothesis and model fit. First of all, descriptive analysis was done to check the demographics information of the respondents. The results indicated that the total 143 responses were collected, from which 47.6% respondents were women and 52.4% respondents were men. 71.3% respondents belonged to age group of 15-25, 21.7% respondents belonged to age group of 26-35, and 5.6% respondents belonged to age group of 35-

45. The education level of respondents was estimated and result showed that 9.8% participants were in intermediate, 43.4% participants were in bachelors, 26.6% participants were in master, 16.8% participants were in MPhil and 3.5% participants were from others (e.g. ACCA). According to results, 58.7% respondents had 25000-45000 income, 14.7% respondents had 46000-65000, 7.0 % respondents had 66000-85000 and 19.6% respondents had income above 85000. For checking the reliability of constructs, reliability analysis was run on SPSS. The values of cronbach alpha were acceptable as the cut off value was above the 0.7 that is suggested by (Hair, Black et al. 1998). The value of Cronbach alpha of constructs varied from 0.769 to 0.922. Confirmatory factor analysis was run on AMOS. The factor loadings varied from 0.61 to 0.81, which are above the limit of 0.6 suggested by (Chin, Gopal et al. 1997). Only three items, one from the measure of CRM, one from the measure of skepticism and one from the measure purchase intention, were eliminated from further analysis because of low factor loading. The convergent validity was checked by composite reliability. All the values varied from 0.661 to 0.829 and are above the limit of 0.6 suggested by (Bagozzi

and Yi 1988). The average variance extracted values are above the cut off value off 0.5 as per (Hair, Black et al. 1998), and varied from 0.501 to 0.560. The detailed values are shown in table 1. The model fit values for confirmatory analysis are above the cut of value suggested by (Bagozzi and Yi 1988) and (Chau and Hu 2001).

The reliability and validity of constructs was checked by measurement model. The second step was to test the hypotheses. For this purpose, the structural equation modeling was used. The model fit values of SEM are acceptable as per the cut off value suggested by (Bagozzi and Yi 1988) and (Chau and Hu 2001). The results of SEM indicated that CRM campaign is a significant construct of purchase intentions with an estimated value of 0.284. To check the moderation effect, interaction method was used. The interaction term is found non-significant having the estimated value of 0.566. It means skepticism does not moderate the relationship between CRM campaign and purchase intention. To measure the mediating effect, the baron and Kenny approach was used (Baron and Kenny 1986). The results indicated that brand image fully mediates the relationship between CRM campaign and purchase intentions. (Table 2)

Table 1: Confirmatory and reliability analysis

Construct	Factor Loading	Internal Reliability Cronbach alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Explained (AVE)
CRM1	0.73	.833	0.688	0.522
CRM2	0.58			
CRM3	0.65			
CRM4	0.66			
CRM5	0.74			
CRM6	0.69			
SK1	0.74	.769	0.722	0.501
SK2	0.77			
SK3	0.63			
SK4	0.56			
BI1	0.63	.922	0.661	0.560
BI2	0.69			
BI3	0.75			
BI4	0.80			
BI5	0.81			
BI6	0.62			
BI7	0.67			
BI8	0.75			

BI9	0.78			
BI10	0.71			
BI11	0.67			
BI12	0.61			
PI1	0.88	.847	0.829	0.543
PI2	0.66			
PI3	0.68			
PI4	0.70			
PI5	0.57			
PI6	0.72			

Table 2: Path coefficients

Hypothesis	Statement	Estimate	Significance	Results
H1	There is a positive significant relationship between CRM campaign and consumer purchase intentions	0.284	0.001	Supported
H2	Skepticism has a moderating effect on the relationship of CRM campaign and purchase intention.	0.566	0.170	Not Supported
H3	Brand image mediates the relationship between the CRM campaign and purchase intentions.	0.287	0.001	Supported

Conclusions and Discussions:

The study is focused on the relationship between CRM campaign and purchase intentions. The research is conducted to find the answers to the research questions mentioned in the first section of the paper. The objective of the study is to promote the cause related marketing in less developed countries like Pakistan. The study also intends to find the effect of skepticism on purchase intentions. For this purpose, quantitative approach is used in this research.

The findings of study reveal that CRM campaign has a positive significant relationship with consumer purchase intentions. These results are supported by previous studies (Shabbir, Kaufmann et al. 2010; Aggarwal and Singh 2019). It indicates that consumers are more likely to purchase the products of brands that are serving a social cause. Cause-related marketing is not only beneficial for earning profits but also fulfills the social responsibility. Consumers feel satisfaction when

they get connected to a cause and help other through their purchase.

The results also show that skepticism has no influence on purchase intentions in context of CRM. Researchers define skepticism as doubt in mind of consumer about the claims for supporting a cause. In this study, the influence of skepticism on purchase intention is found to be non-significant. It is recommended that brands used in this study are well recognized by the respondents. If consumers have any emotional attachment with the brand, it establishes the trust between brand and consumer, and as a result they show less skepticism toward the brand (Patel, Gadhavi et al. 2017). The brand image fully mediates the relationship between the CRM campaign and purchase intention. Brand image is simply a perception of brand in view of consumer.

Implications and Limitations:

This research contributes to the literature regarding cause related marketing in Pakistan. The study is important for academics as well as for practitioners and managers. In academics, it is counted in the few pioneer studies that examined the effect of skepticism on relationship of CRM and consumers purchase intentions. Moreover, it also studied the mediation effect of brand image which is less studied in the context of CRM.

In practical, it helps managers and practitioners to form CRM campaign for their businesses. Cause related marketing is emerging as an effective marketing tool for businesses. CRM can impact the success of organization. Every business aims to earn profit and gain the market share. The biggest challenge for a business is to attain customer retention. Cause related marketing helps the company to establish the long term relation with customers and makes their position strong. The results from the study shows that CRM campaign has positive significant effect on purchase intentions. It proves that customers are more attracted towards the business engaged in serving a social cause. The companies, who are practicing the CRM, show their social responsibility towards the society. It improves their brand image in eyes of customers.

In this study, there are few limitations. We collected data from only one city of Pakistan. Further studies may target other cities as well. In addition, sample size used in this study was small due to short time and lockdown situation during the time of data collection. Future studies may use large sample size in order to increase generalizability.

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